

ISic1418

I.Sicily inscription 1418

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

sandstone

Object

bench

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2018.09.12 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Gymnasium

Coordinates

37.293628, 13.586525

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

Two parallel benches, 45 and 47.5m in length, set out in a north-south direction at a distance of 10m separation. The more easterly bench is designated 'B' by the excavators; the more westerly, 'A'. Each bench is subdivided into two sections, with a seat divider / arm-rest at the end of each section. The inscription is set out over all four sections, beginning at the northern end of Bench B (line 1), proceeding to the southern end of B (line 2), and then continuing on the southern part of Bench A (line 3), and on to the northern section of Bench A (line 4).

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ε[ίςΚ]αίσαρα Αὔγουστον φλάμενος Λουκίου Ἐγνατίου [Λ]ου[κί]ου υιοῦ
Γαλ(ερία)[---]
2. (vac.unknown)~[---]δυῶν δὲ ἀ[νδ]ρῶν
3. Σέξτου Ἐ[να]τ,ίου Σ[έ]ξ[τ]ο[υ]υιοῦ Π[ο]ύφου
4. Λούκιος [ς] Λουκίου υιο[ς][]ο[---][γ]υμνασίαρχος τῶν τε ἐφήβων καὶ
νε[ω]τέρων τοὺς ἀν[κ]λίτας ἐκ τῶν ἰδίων Ἑρμᾶι καὶ Ἡρακλε[ῖ]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644968

EDR 136203 + 136215

EDCS 64900837

PHI 333355

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